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Water Health Open knowLedge (WHOW)

The technical architecture is deployed

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Abstract	<p>This document presents the technical architecture we implemented and deployed for building the WHOW knowledge graph. More specifically, we present: (i) a novel set of reusable components for knowledge graph creation and management, called the WHOW Toolkit; and (ii) a novel semantic knowledge graph for water quality and sanitation.</p>
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0.2	2023-11-08	ARIA	Executive Summary
0.3	2023-11-22	ISPRA	Project overview, objective and relationships with other activities
0.4	2023-11-28	CNR-ISTC	Core implementation concepts
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0.6	2023-12-08	CNR-ISTC	Toolkit components
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1.1	2023-12-31	All	Integration of reviewers' comments

Table of contents

Executive Summary.....	8
1. Introduction.....	9
1.1 Project Overview.....	9
1.2 Objectives.....	9
1.3 Relationships with other activities.....	10
1.4 Structure of the document.....	11
2. Designed technical services.....	12
2.1 High level architecture overview.....	12
3. Developed technical services.....	15
3.1 Core implementation concepts.....	15
3.2 Toolkit components.....	17
3.2.1 DAG Factory.....	19
3.2.2 Data ingester.....	23
3.2.3 Preprocessor.....	24
3.2.4 Triplifier.....	25
3.2.5 Reasoner.....	26
3.2.6 Metadata manager.....	28
3.2.7 Validator.....	31
3.2.8 Multilingual manager.....	33
3.2.9 Triplestore manager.....	34
3.3 Code availability and licence.....	35
4. Knowledge graph.....	36
4.1 Material.....	36
4.2 Method.....	37
4.2.1 Ontology design.....	38
4.2.2 Linked Open Data production.....	39
4.3 Usage examples.....	42
5 Conclusions.....	47
References.....	48

List of Tables

1. [Table 1. Groups of rating for the MQA.](#)
2. [Table 2. Datasets selected for the creation of the WHOW-KG](#)
3. [Table 3. Datasets part of WHOW-KG with their corresponding number of triples.](#)

List of Figures

- [Figure 1. Relationships with other deliverables and activities](#)
- [Figure 2. WHOW high level architecture](#)
- [Figure 3. Abstract representation of the interaction among components by means of Apache Airflow acting as workflow orchestrator.](#)
- [Figure 4. Example of distributed nodes organised in a single workflow orchestrated by a same node providing Apache Airflow.](#)
- [Figure 5. The three modules that are part of a component of the WHOW Toolkit.](#)
- [Figure 6. The UML diagram for the classes implementing the Toolkit components.](#)
- [Figure 7. The Flow ontology.](#)
- [Figure 8. Methodology implemented for constructing the WHOW-KG.](#)
- [Figure 9. Configuration of the WHOW Toolkit used for generating the WHOW-KG for ARIA and ISPRA.](#)
- [Figure 10. The RDF graph that answers the question: What was the concentration of reactive silicates observed for Lake Endine over time?](#)
- [Figure 11. The RDF graph that answers the question: What were the biological agents with their associated concentration recorded over time for the Adriatic sea?](#)
- [Figure 12. Interaction with the WHOW-KG.](#)
- [Figure 13. HTML \(a\) and Turtle \(b\) visualisations of the entity <https://w3id.org/italia/env/ld/water-observation/0076b974d176c9c8887587ae10955f2f>.](#)

Executive Summary

The main goal of the WHOW project is to build an open and distributed knowledge graph that is capable of integrating and standardising heterogeneous data of the environmental and health domains coming from several data sources and available in different formats and structures.

The ultimate goal is fostering the creation of innovative applications, services and studies on top of the WHOW knowledge graph.

Besides the business use cases that are going to be extensively described in deliverable D2.1 to be released at the end of December 2021, a key aspect of the WHOW project is the design of a fully distributed technical architecture for effective creation and publication of the WHOW open and distributed knowledge graph.

This document presents the result of the implementation and deployment of the WHOW Architecture obtained for Milestone #8 (The technical architecture is deployed). The implementation and deployment relies on the analysis and design presented in the Deliverable 4.1¹ [1] and addressing the Milestone #7 (Design of the technical services for knowledge graph management is finalised). More specifically, the document presents our outcomes in terms of: (i) a set of reusable components for knowledge graph creation and management, called the WHOW Toolkit, that we implemented in the context of the WHOW project; and (ii) a novel semantic knowledge graph for water quality and sanitation. The WHOW Toolkit and knowledge graph are further integrated in a broader software deployment that includes existing open source solutions we reused for providing interaction capabilities to users, being them either humans or applications. By interaction capabilities we mean accessing, querying, and visualising the knowledge graph as well as using the services provided by the WHOW Toolkit. These are exposed through REST API or WebSocket interfaces depending on specific cases that we detail in next chapters and sections.

¹ <https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.6685696>

1. Introduction

This is the Deliverable 4.2 that reports the results associated with the milestone #8 titled “The technical architecture is deployed”. The milestone and deliverable are part of the Activity 4, which is focused on the implementation of the technical architecture. More specifically, this document reports on the outcomes of the tasks 4.2 and 4.3, titled “Development of the technical services for knowledge graph management” and “APIs production and deployment”, respectively. It extends the Deliverable 4.1 [1] that reports the outcome of the milestone #7² we reached in the context of the task 4.1 focused on the design of the technical services for knowledge graph management.

1.1 Project Overview

The WHOW project aims to foster the creation of the first open and distributed European knowledge graph on water consumption and quality, health parameters and dissemination of diseases to be reused for advanced analysis and development of innovative services.

The project leverages the Linked Open Data paradigm. Water related datasets from Italy and other European countries and Copernicus (the European Union's Earth observation programme) will be used to support the construction of WHOW's knowledge graph, intended as a federation of knowledge graphs deployed at each data provider willing to join the WHOW community. The knowledge graph will be documented on data.europa.eu, the official portal for European data, thanks to the adoption of shared metadata models such as DCAT-AP and its extensions that are relevant for the type of data treated in WHOW (e.g., GeoDCAT-AP). Selected health related datasets mainly from Italy will be linked to specific water datasets.

WHOW targets identified use cases in the creation of the knowledge graph. In order to evaluate such use cases relevant set of indicators for Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) are identified along with Key Performance Indicators for metadata and data quality. A co-creation programme, where interested stakeholders and users are engaged from the initial phases of the project, is set-up so as to consider real needs of data re-users.

The initiative supports the Public Open Data Digital Service Infrastructure by helping to boost the development of information products and services based on the re-use and combination of environmental data and health data on disease dissemination.

1.2 Objectives

This document presents the result of the implementation and deployment of the WHOW Architecture obtained for Milestone #8 (The technical architecture is deployed). The implementation and deployment relies on the analysis and design presented in the Deliverable 4.1³ [1] and addressing the Milestone #7 (Design of the technical services for knowledge graph management is finalised). Hence, we first recall

² Design of the technical services for knowledge graph management is finalised.

³ <https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.6685696>

general concepts on the high-level architecture we designed, then we describe the implementation of such an architecture, which consists of a software platform. The latter includes: (i) a set of reusable components for knowledge graph creation and management, called the WHOW Toolkit, that we implemented in the context of the WHOW project; and (ii) a novel semantic knowledge graph for water quality and sanitation. The WHOW Toolkit and knowledge graph are further integrated in a broader software deployment that includes existing open source solutions we reused for providing interaction capabilities to users, being them either humans or applications. By interaction capabilities we mean accessing, querying, and visualising the knowledge graph as well as using the services provided by the WHOW Toolkit. These are exposed through REST API or WebSocket interfaces depending on specific cases that we detail in next chapters and sections.

1.3 Relationships with other activities

The present deliverable D4.2 is an important milestone (#8) of the WHOW project. It covers all the activities of task 4.2 and 4.3 of Activity 4 that have dependencies with other tasks and activities of the project. Figure 1 shows such relationships. In particular, the content of this deliverable is related to: (i) the definition of the use cases and the preliminary data quality requirements, (ii) the design of the technical architecture, and (iii) the development of the use cases. In addition, relationships with the on-going work of the semantic data model of the knowledge graph of WHOW are identified when semantic indicators are described and included in the framework introduced in this document.

Figure 1. Relationships with other deliverables and activities

1.4 Structure of the document

The rest of this document is structured as follows. [Section 2](#) summarises the architecture design. [Section 3](#) describes the implementation of such an architecture extensively. [Section 4](#) details on the knowledge graph. Finally, [Section 5](#) concludes the document.

2. Designed technical services

The present chapter summarises: (i) the technical services that we designed to create and manage the WHOW knowledge graph and (ii) the knowledge graph itself with its associated technicalities. Hence, it includes a description of the software we implemented in a modular and decentralised fashion.

2.1 High level architecture overview

The high-level designed Linked (Open) Data architecture is depicted in Figure 2. It consists of a modular structure which encompasses several layers, transporting the original information from inhomogeneous data to a final structured form available to users. Although this general scheme can be developed differently among data providers, it keeps the same overall structure and components.

It is a fully distributed architecture that allows different data providers, also from various European member states, to build, manage over time and publish their own decentralised knowledge graphs, which together form the so-called WHOW knowledge graph, along with associated services.

The architecture, to be deployed by each data provider, is designed as a five-layer architecture consisting of the:

- *data preparation layer*, responsible for extracting knowledge both from the internal sources of the WHOW project data providers and from external sources managed by other stakeholders, not directly participating in WHOW. All data sources can potentially be very heterogeneous both in formats and structures;

Figure 2. WHOW high level architecture

- *knowledge graph layer* which includes the domain-dependent semantic assets to be produced and published. In particular, the main components of this layer are both shared ontologies and reference data (i.e., controlled vocabularies), used to model the WHOW knowledge, and data represented using those ontologies and reference data, published in the form of Linked Open Data (LOD). All these semantic assets are expressed using open semantic web open standards and formats (e.g., OWL, RDF), and are associated with an open standard license (e.g., Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 - CC-BY 4.0, Creative Commons Public Domain - CC0) so as to maximize their re-use by anyone;
- *knowledge graph service management layer*, responsible for providing the set of software components that are used to manage the underlying knowledge graph layer. This layer consists of all those services that allow the actors, identified in the earlier Section 3, to manage the different elements of the knowledge graph, from metadata, network of ontologies up to the linked open data, with a focus on the multilingual and semantic linking aspects of this latter. It is in this layer that:
 - (Geo)DCAT-AP metadata, also compliant with national extensions, is properly managed. This allows data providers to make their knowledge graph resources harvestable by the European Data portal (data.europa.eu) and other catalogues of reference (e.g., national open data catalogues, European geospatial data catalogue);
 - the lifecycle of the network of ontologies and reference data is managed, spanning from versioning management, necessary for capturing the possible changes over time of the semantic assets, to semantic inference and consistency checks, required as a form of verification of the robustness of the produced semantic assets;
 - linked open data management activities are performed. In fact, this layer includes services for data validation against ontologies and reference data, data multilinguality, through the use of CEF building blocks such as e-Translation, data linking to create semantic links among different datasets, and any other CRUD operations on the linked open data;
- *application layer and presentation layer*, responsible for supporting all those use cases that have been identified related to the consumption by end-users and software agents of the knowledge graph. Therefore, these layers embody all those components that enable both a human-based (UI of the presentation layer in Figure 7) and a machine-based interaction (API of the presentation layer in Figure 7), where searching and accessing functionalities are provided. SPARQL endpoint instances for data and ontology network access are part of this layer as well as all those software components that will allow WHOW data providers to offer APIs defined via REST, using standards such as OpenAPI⁴. The application layer may also include specific business dependent functionalities.

The lines in Figure 7 represent communications among the layers, and thus among their components.

It is worth noting that the architecture has been designed to be independent of the specific water and health application domains of WHOW. With the exception of the knowledge graph layer where inevitably

⁴ <https://swagger.io/specification/>.

the elements are strongly dependent on the characteristics of these domains, the other layers and services of the architecture are sufficiently general to be applied in any Linked Open Data technical scenario, making the proposed architecture a so-called *reference architecture*.

In addition, some services may be viewed as mandatory in order to publish Linked Open Data (i.e., SPARQL endpoint, Triplifier): without them there is no possibility to create and publish a knowledge graph; other services can be thought of as additional services whose aim is to contribute to the creation of a more comprehensive toolkit where also all the aspects of data quality are taken into account (examples include the validation service, semantic search, indexing/caching).

3. Developed technical services

The architecture described in [Section 2](#) drove to the implementation of the WHOW Toolkit. The WHOW Toolkit is a Python modular software, which is based on the component-based architectural style. As pointed out in the Deliverable 4.1 [1], the component-based architectural style describes a software engineering approach to system design and development. It focuses on the decomposition of the design into individual functional or logical components that expose well-defined communication interfaces containing methods, events, and properties. This provides a high level of abstraction, even higher than object-oriented design principles, and does not focus on issues such as communication protocols and shared states. The key principle of the component-based style is the use of components that are software packages, web services, web resources, or modules that encapsulate a set of related functions and data.

3.1 Core implementation concepts

The WHOW Toolkit provides a set of reusable and independent software components for dealing with the creation and management of large knowledge graphs, like the one we constructed in the context of the project. The communication among the components is limited to and enabled by specific interfaces. The latter are based either on REST API over HTTP or WebSocket API. The REST API relies on conventional one-directional connections over HTTP(s). On the contrary, WebSocket API makes it possible to open a two-way interactive communication session between two components identified as a client and server, respectively. With WebSocket, it is possible to send messages to a server and receive event-driven responses without having to poll the server for a reply. The choice between the REST API or WebSocket API depends on specific implementation needs as they provide different services as well as different architectural integrations for final deployment.

The typical interaction with the WHOW Toolkit is based on the definition of workflows aimed at the creation of RDF datasets from non-RDF sources (e.g. CSV, XML, JSON, etc.) for populating a broader knowledge graph. The workflows are represented as Python code, which defines directed acyclic graphs (DAGs) of tasks based on the Apache Airflow⁵ platform. Apache Airflow is an open-source platform for developing, scheduling, and monitoring batch-oriented workflows. Airflow's extensible Python framework enables a developer to build workflows connecting with virtually any technology.

Each component of the WHOW Toolkit is designed and implemented to be deployed as a task of a DAG that can be executed by Apache Airflow. The communication between the Python code implementing a DAG and the components of the Toolkit identifying its tasks is enabled by the WebSocket API exposed by those components. The objective of a DAG is to define the workflow, whilst the objective of Airflow is to orchestrate the execution of the components part of a workflow by means of WebSocket requests. Figure 3 depicts an abstract representation of the interaction among components by means of Apache Airflow that acts as workflow orchestrator. In such a Figure the Task 1 is the first to be executed, whilst Task N is the last one in the workflow. The workflow is represented by the arrows labelled "next" that connect tasks. Once a task part of a workflow orchestrated by Airflow is executed then it triggers a Toolkit component by means of a WebSocket request. For example, Task 1 triggers the Component A and Task n triggers the Component Z, respectively. With this configuration each component of the Toolkit is completely unaware of and independent from any other component of the Toolkit. Once a component is triggered through a

⁵ <https://github.com/apache/airflow>

WebSocket request it starts its computation and returns back a message to the Airflow task that triggered its execution. Input and return messages are JSON strings that contain information about how to get input or output resources. In most cases those are references to REST API that can be used to retrieve the required resource. For example, if the component triggered by Airflow is an RDFizer (a component that accepts as input a non-RDF source and produces RDF as output) it might accept a JSON message that contains an HTTP(s) reference to a non-RDF source to be processed. Accordingly, the same component might produce as output a JSON message containing the URI of the RDF produced that can be used to get the resource through REST over HTTP(s). We will detail the specific input required and generated by the components in the next sections.

Figure 3. Abstract representation of the interaction among components by means of Apache Airflow acting as workflow orchestrator.

The WHOW Toolkit is designed and implemented to deploy fully distributed frameworks. That is, different components can be installed in different nodes and exposed and accessed remotely by an AirFlow instance via their corresponding WebSocket server provided by the Toolkit itself. This allows different data providers, also from various European member, to be part of the WHOW infrastructure by (i) reusing existing services already provided by other members of the infrastructure (e.g. reasoning component, metadating component, etc.) or (ii) configure, customise, and deploy the components they require. An example of distributed configuration of the WHOW Toolkit focused on the creation of workflows for knowledge graph creation is shown in Figure 4. In this Figure all the components are represented as different nodes that can

be reached through WebSocket protocol and orchestrated in a workflow-like process by another independent node that provides Apache Airflow.

Figure 4. Example of distributed nodes organised in a single workflow orchestrated by a same node providing Apache Airflow.

3.2 Toolkit components

Internally each component of the Toolkit is divided into three modules, i.e.:

- **Core Module:** it provides the core business functionalities implemented by the component. For example a component of the Toolkit for converting non-RDF sources to RDF has classes, methods, and functions for interacting with an RML engine that actually performs the conversion based on declarative mappings;
- **REST Module:** it provides the REST API that can be used for accessing the core business functionalities via HTTP(s) requests. For example, the same component as before for converting non-RDF sources to RDF exposes a REST interface that can be accessed through a HTTP(s) GET request for accessing the resulting RDF generated after the execution of an RML mapping. The REST

API supports content negotiation in order to serve the appropriate content depending on the request. HTML is always supported for enabling human-readable interfaces towards the REST API.

- **WebSocket Module:** it provides a component with API that can be accessed through the WebSocket protocol. The REST API and WebSocket API are not alternative, but complementary. In fact, the REST API can be used for interacting with a component in a fully Web-based context that requires responsive services that take no longer than a few seconds for their execution. Instead, the WebSocket API focuses on serving a component's functionalities that require longer execution times (e.g. reasoning or mapping).

Figure 5 shows an exemplification of the internal division of a component in the three modules we just described. For the sake of simplicity, in the Figure a single component is presented for a Toolkit node part of the WHOW infrastructure. However, a single node can have multiple components whose functionalities can be accessed externally through either the WebSocket or HTTP(s) protocols.

Figure 5. The three modules that are part of a component of the WHOW Toolkit.

It is worth saying that in a few cases a component can have only the REST module or WebSocket one. We will provide more details about this when describing the single components we implemented.

The component-based architectural style is implemented in the WHOW toolkit thanks to iPOPO⁶. iPOPO is a Python-based Service-Oriented Component Model (SOCM) based on Pelix⁷, which is a dynamic service platform. iPOPO is inspired by two popular Java technologies for the development of long-lived

⁶ <https://ipopo.readthedocs.io/en/1.0.1/>

⁷ <https://pypi.org/project/jsonrplib-pelix/>

applications: the iPOJO component model [2] and the OSGi Service Platform⁸ [3]. iPOJO enables the conception of long-running and modular IT services.

Currently, the Toolkit has the components as presented in the UML class diagram depicted in Figure 6. The interface `ToolkitComponent` is the most general class to implement the core part of a component of the Toolkit. Those components are further described in the following subsections.

Figure 6. The UML diagram for the classes implementing the Toolkit components.

3.2.1 DAG Factory

The DAG Factory allows the creation, management, and deletion of Python code that implements the directed acyclic graphs (DAGs) of tasks required by Apache Airflow to execute workflow. The DAG factory addresses the requirement FR-01⁹ defined in the deliverable 4.1¹⁰ [1]. The component provides a REST API module only, thus it cannot be accessed via WebSocket. The DAG factory has to be configured in order to use a declared installation of Apache Airflow and it must be granted access to the folder used by Airflow for storing DAGs (e.g. `/path/dags`). Another configuration parameter is the HTTP endpoint. Both configuration parameters are passed in a JSON file located inside the folder `conf` of the DAG Factory. The structure of the JSON file is the following.

```
{
  "dags.folder": "$AIRFLOW_HOME/dags/",
}
```

⁸ <https://docs.osgi.org/download/r3/r3.book.pdf>

⁹ The platform shall support the definition of automated data cleaning, processing, transformation and publication pipelines involving datasets originating from the data providers' internal/existing systems and from external data sources.

¹⁰ <https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.6685696>

```

    "http.endpoint": "http://localhost:5000/"
  }

```

Hence, the core module allows one to create a new workflow and instantiate it inside the folder for DAGs managed by Airflow. Such a workflow is created from an RDF file accepted as input that represents the workflow. The RDF file can be passed either as a URI referring to the RDF on the Web or as a proper RDF file serialised in all most used serialisation, i.e. RDF/XML, Turtle, N3, NTriples, and JSON-LD. The RDF file is modelled according to the Flow ontology¹¹, which is a simple schema for representing plans we modelled in the context of the project by reusing the sequence ontology design pattern¹². The Flow ontology is depicted in Figure 7 with the Graffoo notation¹³ [4]. The ontology allows to represent a workflow as an instance of the class `flow:Plan` that can be linked to instances of `flow:Activity` that represent tasks in the sense of Airflow. The sequence of tasks of a workflow can be obtained by means of the object property `flow:hasNextActivity`, or its inverse `flow:hasPreviousActivity`, which is defined as transitive.

Figure 7. The Flow ontology.

An example of RDF file that can be used for generating a Airflow DAG is the following:

```

@prefix : <https://w3id.org/whow/data/workflow/> .
@prefix flow: <https://w3id.org/whow/onto/flow/> .
@prefix dcat: <http://www.w3.org/ns/dcat#> .
@prefix dcatapit: <http://dati.gov.it/onto/dcatapit#> .
@prefix dct: <http://purl.org/dc/terms/> .
@prefix foaf: <http://xmlns.com/foaf/0.1/> .

```

¹¹ <https://w3id.org/whow/onto/flow>

¹² <http://ontologydesignpatterns.org/wiki/Submissions:Sequence>

¹³ <https://essepuntato.it/graffoo/>

```

@prefix prov: <http://www.w3.org/ns/prov#> .
@prefix tvo: <https://data.europa.eu/m8g/transform-validate-ontology#> .
@prefix xsd: <http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#> .
@prefix rdfs: <http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#> .
@prefix wfm: <https://w3id.org/whow/onto/workflow-mgmt/> .

:Plan a flow:Plan ;
  rdfs:label "The Plan"@en ;
  flow:hasFirstActivity :Ingestion .

:Ingestion a flow:Activity ;
  rdfs:label "The data ingestion activity"@en ;
  flow:hasBoundService flow:ingestion ;
  flow:hasNextActivity :Cleansing .

:Cleansing a flow:Activity ;
  rdfs:label "The data cleansing activity"@en ;
  flow:hasBoundService flow:preprocessing ;
  flow:hasNextActivity :Mapping .

:Mapping a flow:Activity ;
  rdfs:label "The data mapping activity with RML"@en ;
  flow:hasBoundService flow:mapping ;
  flow:hasNextActivity :Metadating .

:Metadating a flow:Activity ;
  rdfs:label "The metadata creation activity with RML"@en ;
  flow:hasBoundService flow:metadating ;
  flow:hasNextActivity :Validation .

:Validation a flow:Activity ;
  rdfs:label "The validation activity."@en ;
  flow:hasBoundService flow:validation ;
  flow:hasNextActivity :Storing .

:Storing a flow:Activity ;
  rdfs:label "The data are stored in a triplestore"@en ;
  flow:hasBoundService flow:storing .

```

The RDF above instantiates a DAG with four tasks, i.e. data cleansing, RDF mapping, metadating, data validation, and RDF data storing. Once the DAG has been instantiated then it can be executed by DAG Factory.

The DAG Factory is implemented by the Python class `DAGFactory` available in the core module of the component. This class has the methods listed below.

```
create(rdf: str, dag_id: str) -> DAG
```

It creates and instantiates a DAG in Airflow from an RDF provided either as file or URI. If no error is raised the method does not return any value as output.

```
delete(dag_id: str) -> None
```

It deletes a DAG from Airflow by using the identifier of the DAG as a reference.

```
execute(dag_id: str, config: json) -> json
```

The method above executes the DAG identified by the argument `dag_id` by using the JSON value of the `config` argument as input of the DAG. The method triggers the DAG on the Airflow instance with the specific configuration as input. The triggering is performed by means of the REST API exposed by Airflow. The output of the execution is a JSON string that reports a success or failure status with additional references to the output produced by the workflow execution.

The input JSON bound to the `config` argument has the following structure:

```
{
  "bound_services": {
    "SERVICE_ID": {
      "endpoint": "ws://PATH_TO_SERVICE/",
      "data": {...}
    }
  }
}
```

Where:

- `SERVICE_ID` has to be replaced with an instance of the class `flow:Service` as defined in the Flow ontology (e.g. `flow:ingestion`, `flow:mapping`, etc.);
- `endpoint` has to be associated with a value representing the endpoint providing the implementation of the service via WebSocket protocol;
- `data` contains the data to pass to the service as input value.

The methods implemented by the class `DAGFactory` can be accessed through the REST module of the component that provides the following API:

```
POST /dagfactory
```

- Description: it allows the creation and instantiation of a DAG.
- Params:
 - `rdf_uri`: the string value representing the URI where the RDF representation of the workflow is available. This parameter is alternative to `rdf_content`;

- `dag_id`: the string value representing the identifier that will be associated with the new DAG.

POST /dagfactory/<DAG_ID>

- Description: it allows the execution of the DAG identified by the path argument <DAG_ID>.
- Params:
 - `config`: the JSON object describing additional configuration parameters.

DELETE /dagfactory/<DAG_ID>

- Description: it allows the deletion of the DAG identified by the path argument <DAG_ID>.

3.2.2 Data ingester

The Data ingester is the component aimed at ingesting external non-RDF datasets into the Toolkit. It is implemented by the class `SimpleIngester` that addresses the requirements FR-02 and FR-03 of the Data acquisition use case (UC-0101) as defined in the Deliverable 4.1 [1]. Such a class provides the following method below that accepts an RDF graph as input representing a catalogue, dataset or distribution description according to DCAT_AP. Hence, it retrieves and downloads all possible distributions from this description.

```
do_job(input: Graph) -> None
```

Additionally, the class `SimpleIngester` provides the following methods:

- `get_data_collection(dcid: str) -> DataCollection`
That returns a `DataCollection` object from its identifier (i.e. the `dcid` argument), which is the description of catalogue, dataset or distribution previously ingested by the system. This method addresses the functional requirement FR-45 of the architectural design.
- `delete_data_collection(dcid: str) -> None`
That deletes a `DataCollection` object identified by the `dcid` argument from the system.

The previous two methods can be accessed through the REST API exposed by the REST module. Namely:

GET /data/<dataset_id>

- Description: it allows the retrieval of a dataset identified by the `dataset_id` path parameter.

DELETE /data/<dataset_id>

- Description: it allows the deletion of a dataset identified by the `dataset_id` path parameter.

The data ingestion is exposed through the WebSocket protocol and can be part of a DAG workflow as a task. The WebSocket service of the Data ingester is associated with the path `/ingestion`. Such a service accepts a JSON message as input like the following:

```
{ "title": "Hydrolakes data",
  "description": "Analytical data on the substances monitored at points in
the Lombardy Region lake monitoring network.",
  "distributions": [
    {"id": "hydrolakes",
     "mimetype": "text/csv",
     "downloadURL":
"https://hub.dati.lombardia.it/resource/d4ep-yvbw.csv"}
  ]
}
```

In the JSON message above there is a dataset with a distribution that can be downloaded thanks to the value bound to the key `downloadURL`.

The JSON message can be associated with the `data` key of the JSON configuration provided to the DAG Factory component via its REST API as described in [Section 3.2.1](#).

3.2.3 Preprocessor

Data preprocessing is of utmost importance for normalising and cleansing data before transforming them to RDF. A dedicated deliverable¹⁴ describes the core activities focused on data preprocessing in WHOW [5].

In the core module the Preprocessor is implemented by the class `DataPreprocessor`, which addresses the requirement FR-08¹⁵ of the architectural design by providing the method:

```
do_job(self, input: DataCollection, *args, **kwargs) -> dict:
```

This method accepts a `DataCollection` object as input and performs all preprocessing operations on this object. The method can be invoked via WebSocket through the endpoint `/preprocessor`. The WebSocket service accepts a JSON message as input like the following:

```
"ids": ["distribution_id_1", "distribution_id_2", ..., distribution_id_n]
```

where `distribution_id_1`, `distribution_id_2`, and `distribution_id_n` have to be replaced with a dataset identifier as specified during the ingestion procedure, e.g. `hydrolakes`.

The REST API can be used to get or delete a non-RDF distribution of a dataset after its preprocessing. The HTTP request for getting such a distribution is the following:

```
GET /preprocessor/<distro_id>
```

In the request above the path parameter `<distro_id>` has to be replaced with the identifier of the distribution, e.g. `hydrolakes`, according to our previous example.

¹⁴ Deliverable 3.1: Data pre-processing is finalised. <https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.6685784>

¹⁵ The platform shall provide an extensible and pluggable set of data cleaning and transformation services. In the case specific privacy preserving operations are needed when the data is acquired in WHOW, the transformation services shall deal with them.

Instead, the HTTP request for deleting the internal representation of a distribution after its preprocessing is the following:

```
DELETE /preprocessor/<distro_id>
```

Again, the path parameter `<distro_id>` has to be replaced with the identifier of the distribution, e.g. [hydrolakes](#).

3.2.4 Triplifier

The Triplifier is the component able to transform content to linked data. Our implementation relies on the RDF Mapping language¹⁶ (RML) [6]. RML allows one to express customised mapping rules from heterogeneous data structures and serialisations to the RDF data model. RML is defined as a superset of the W3C-standardised mapping language R2RML¹⁷, aiming to extend its applicability and broaden its scope, adding support for data in other structured formats. The default implementation of Triplifier uses pyRML¹⁸, is a lightweight Python engine to process RML mappings. pyRML was designed and implemented by CNR in the context of the WHOW project and it is released as open source with an Apache 2.0 licence¹⁹. Alternatively, the Triplifier can be configured to use the RMLMapper²⁰, which is a Java base engine to process RML mappings.

In the core module the Triplifier is implemented by the class `PYRMLMapper`, which addresses the requirement FR-07²¹ and related sub-requirements of the architectural design by providing the method:

```
do_job(self, input: MapperInput, *args, **kwargs):
```

This method accepts a `MapperInput` object as input and invokes the RML-based execution of mappings. A `MapperInput` provides the Triplifier with the references to the RML mappings and the RDF graph to generate as output. A `MapperInput` can be seen a JSON object like the following:

```
{ "graphs": [
  { "id": "RMLMappinghydrolakes",
    "rmls": [
      { "uri": "https://t.ly/J401f" }
    ]
  }
]}
```

¹⁶ <https://rml.io/>

¹⁷ <https://www.w3.org/TR/r2rml/>

¹⁸ <https://github.com/anuzzolese/pyrml>

¹⁹ <https://www.apache.org/licenses/LICENSE-2.0.txt>

²⁰ <https://github.com/RMLio/rmlmapper-java>

²¹ The platform shall enable the definition and management of data transformation/mapping rules for the processing of datasets in heterogeneous formats.

In the object above a list of graphs is described in terms of (i) their IDs and (ii) the RML scripts (e.g. "<https://t.ly/J401f>") to execute in order to generate those graphs.

JSON objects like the one just described can be used as input to send to the WebSocket module of the Triplifier. Once the WebSocket module receives a message containing a JSON object like the previous, the Triplifier is requested to start the generation of RDF triples based on the RML mappings provided as input. The WebSocket module of the Triplifier accepts requests to the path `/mapping`.

All generated RDF graphs are then available for download as dumps in different RDF serialisations (e.g. Turtle, RDF/XML, N-Triples, etc.) via HTTP requests. The latter functionality covers the requirements FR-44²² and FR-46²³. For example, an RDF graph can be downloaded by sending a GET request like the following:

```
GET /mapper/<graph_id>
```

In the request above the path parameter `<graph_id>` has to be replaced with the identifier of the graph, e.g. `RMLMappinghydrolakes`, which is specified in the JSON object provided as input to the Triplifier component.

A specific RDF serialisation of a graph can be obtained via content negotiation. For example, the following request performed with cURL specifies the RDF/XML serialisation in the Accept header.

```
curl -H "Accept: application/rdf+xml" \  
http://localhost:5000/mapper/RMLMappinghydrolakes
```

In the request above the endpoint `localhost:5000` should be replaced with the address of the server hosting the WHOW Toolkit.

Similarly, an RDF graph can be removed from those available for download from the Triplifier endpoint by means of HTTP DELETE request, that is

```
DELETE /mapper/<graph_id>
```

3.2.5 Reasoner

The Reasoner is the component meant for implementing Description Logics (DL) reasoning in the WHOW Toolkit. A DL reasoner is a software tool or system designed to perform automated reasoning tasks based on the principles of Description Logics. Description Logics is a family of formal knowledge representation languages, and they are often used in artificial intelligence and knowledge-based systems.

The key functionalities of the Reasoner include subsumption checking (determining if one concept is more general than another), instance checking (determining if an individual belongs to a certain concept), consistency checking (ensuring that a knowledge base does not contain contradictions), and inference. Namely, the reasoner can be used to enrich a knowledge graph produced by the Triplifier by inferring and materialising new triples.

²² The user shall be able to download RDF data as dump files in RDF open format, e.g. RDF turtle, RDF/XML, JSON-LD.

²³ The data provider shall be able to export his/her data in different RDF serialisations or formats.

The core module of the Reasoner component relies on the library Owlready2²⁴ [7] to use Pellet [8] for DL reasoning. The reasoning capabilities address the requirements FR-09²⁵ and FR-17²⁶ that can be accessed when invoking the method `do_reasoning` of the class `PelletReasoner` part of the core module. The signature of such a method is reported below.

```
do_job(self, ontolgy_network: List[URIRef], data: List[URIRef]) -> Graph
```

The method `do_reasoning` accepts two arguments as input, i.e.

- `ontolgy_network`, which is a list or URI referring to a network of ontologies to use as the terminological box (TBox) for reasoning;
- `data`, which is a list of URI referring to RDF graphs to use for materialising new knowledge by means of reasoning.

The output is an RDF graph, that is one for each graph received as input.

The reasoning provided by the core module can be executed via the WebSocket interface by sending a JSON message to the WebSocket module of the Reasoning component. This message has the following structure:

```
[
  {
    "graph_id": "RMLMappinghydrolakes",
    "ontologies": [
      "https://w3id.org/whow/onto/health-monitoring",
      "https://w3id.org/whow/onto/hydrography"
    ],
    "graphs": [
      "https://www.example.org/graph1",
      "https://www.example.org/graph2",
      "https://www.example.org/graph3"
    ]
  }
]
```

The JSON message is a list of objects structured in three parts:

- the `graph_id` used for providing an identifier to the graph resulting from the reasoning task;
- the list of `ontologies` used to define the TBox;
- the list of `graphs` used to define the ABox.

When a reasoning task, previously triggered through the WebSocket interface, terminates its execution, then the resulting RDF graphs can be accessed and downloaded via REST API over HTTP(s). A GET and a DELETE requests are enabled. The GET is structured in the following way:

²⁴ <https://owlready2.readthedocs.io/en/v0.42/>

²⁵ The platform shall provide an extensible and pluggable set of data linking services.

²⁶ The platform shall support data interoperability, also in the presence of new upcoming data and thus new data requirements, and the rules for generating semantic relationships/links between data items and entities within different linked data sources and datasets (cross-site datasets interlinking and linking to external datasets/knowledge graphs).

```
GET /reasoner/<graph_id>
```

In the request above the path parameter `<graph_id>` has to be replaced with the identifier of the graph, e.g. `RMLMappinghydrolakes`, which is specified in the JSON object provided as input to the Reasoner component.

A specific RDF serialisation of a graph can be obtained via content negotiation. For example, the following request performed with cURL specify the RDF/XML serialisation in the Accept header.

```
curl -H "Accept: application/rdf+xml" \  
http://localhost:5000/reasoner/RMLMappinghydrolakes
```

In the request above the endpoint `localhost:5000` should be replaced with the address of the server hosting the WHOW Toolkit.

Similarly, an RDF graph can be removed from those available for download from the Reasoner endpoint by means of HTTP DELETE request, that is

```
DELETE /reasoner/<graph_id>
```

3.2.6 Metadata manager

The Metadata Manager requires as input a reference (i.e. a URI) to an RDF graph, a configuration file with .ini extension, and two URIs for identifying in the metadata catalogue the dataset and the distribution. The configuration file consists of a text-based content with a structure and syntax comprising key–value pairs for properties, and sections that organise the properties. The keys are DCAT-AP properties and values are their corresponding valorisation. Those key–value pairs can be organised into two sections, i.e. one for DCAT-AP metadata for describing a dataset and another for DCAT-AP metadata for describing a dataset distribution. The Metadata Manager uses the dataset URI provided as input to retrieve existing metadata available in the catalogue. The output produced by the Metadata Manager is an RDF representation of the configuration file, which is eventually enriched with already existing metadata from the catalogue and packaged along with the input RDF dataset for further processing (e.g. Validation). The following is an example of a configuration file, in which sections are coloured in red, whilst key-value pairs are separated by the = symbol.

```
[dataset]  
# https://w3id.org/italia/env/ld/bathw/dataset  
dct:identifier='ispra_rm:bathw_Series'  
dct:title='Dataset acque di balneazione'@it  
dct:title='Bathing waters Dataset'@en  
dct:description='Dataset indicatori acque di balneazione'@it  
dct:description='Bathing Water Indicator Dataset'@en  
dcat:theme=<http://publications.europa.eu/resource/authority/data-theme/ENVI>  
dct:modified='2023-11-01'^^xsd:date  
dct:rightsHolder=<https://w3id.org/italia/env/ld/common/organisation/001>  
dct:accrualPeriodicity=<http://publications.europa.eu/resource/authority/frequency/AN  
NUAL>
```

dct:subject=<http://eurovoc.europa.eu/600>
dcat:contactPoint=<https://w3id.org/italia/env/ld/common/organization/001-LD>
dct:publisher=<https://w3id.org/italia/env/ld/common/organisation/001>
dct:creator=<https://w3id.org/italia/env/ld/common/organisation/001>
dct:issued='2023-11-01'^^xsd:date
dct:language=<http://publications.europa.eu/resource/authority/language/ITA>
dct:language=<http://publications.europa.eu/resource/authority/language/ENG>
dcat:keyword='open data'@it
dcat:keyword='open data'@en
dcat:keyword='balneazione'@it
dcat:keyword='bathing'@en
dcat:keyword='mare'@it
dcat:keyword='sea'@en
dcat:keyword='turismo'@it
dcat:keyword='tourism'@en
dcat:keyword='salute'@it
dcat:keyword='health'@en
dct:temporal=<https://w3id.org/italia/env/ld/common/timeinterval/20220101_today>
dct:spatial=<https://w3id.org/italia/controlled-vocabulary/territorial-classifications/countries/italy/ITA>
dct:spatial=<http://publications.europa.eu/resource/authority/country/ITA>
dct:spatial=<https://www.geonames.org/3175395>
dct:accessRights=<http://publications.europa.eu/resource/authority/access-right/PUBLIC>
prov:wasDerivedFrom=<https://doi.org/10.2909/5d9a4d94-511a-486d-afbb-4f01e5c73e23>

[distribution]

<https://w3id.org/italia/env/ld/bathw/distribution/nt>
dcat:accessURL=<https://dati.isprambiente.it/sparql>
dct:format=<http://publications.europa.eu/resource/authority/file-type/RDF_N_TRIPLES>
dct:license=<https://w3id.org/italia/controlled-vocabulary/licences/A21_CCBY40>
dct:description='Distribuzione RDF con serializzazione N-TRIPLES del dataset indicatori acque di balneazione'@it
dct:description='RDF distribution with N-TRIPLES serialisation of the bathing water indicators dataset'@en
dct:title='Distribuzione RDF con serializzazione N-TRIPLES del dataset acque di balneazione'@it
dct:title='RDF distribution with N-TRIPLES serialisation of the bathing water dataset'@en
dcat:downloadURL=<https://rep.isprambiente.it/downloads/lod/rdf/bathw/kg>
dct:modified='2023-11-01'^^xsd:date
dcat:mediaType=<https://www.iana.org/assignments/media-types/application/n-triples>
dct:rights=<http://publications.europa.eu/resource/authority/access-right/PUBLIC>
dct:issued='2023-11-01'^^xsd:date

Those inputs are packaged within an object named `MetadataInput` and passed to the method `do_job` of an instance of the class `DCATMetadataCreator`, which implements the core functionalities of the Metadata manager component.

```
do_job(self, input: MetadataInput, *args, **kwargs) -> Graph
```

The output of the method `DCATMetadataCreator.do_job()` is an RDF graph that contains the metadata associated with the RDF distribution of a given dataset. Those metadata are formalised according to the DCAT Application Profile for data portals in Europe²⁷ (DCAP-AP).

The Metadata manager component addresses the requirements FR-14²⁸, FR-15²⁹, FR-16³⁰ and their related sub-requirements as elicited in the Deliverable 4.1 for architectural design [1].

The interaction with the core module is enabled by the WebSocket interface provided by the corresponding module available for the component. The WebSocket module accepts through its interface a JSON object as input to start the communication with the core module (i.e. the `DCATMetadataCreator` class). The schema of this JSON is exemplified below.

```
[
  {
    "id": "RMLMappinghydrolakes",
    "dataset_id": "https://hub.dati.lombardia.it/resource/d4ep-yvbw",
    "distribution_id": "https://hub.dati.lombardia.it/resource/d4ep-yvbw-rdf",
    "configuration": "http://host.docker.internal/whow/config_test.ini"
  }
]
```

The JSON is a list of objects that provide the meta-level information for generating the metadata of a dataset distribution. The key "id" key is used to identify the RDF graph to annotate. This value is useful for merging all the output of the different components of the WHOW Toolkit when they are organised and executed in a workflow (cf. DAG Factory in [Section 3.2.1](#)). The `dataset_id` key identifies the dataset with a URI. This is used to retrieve existing metadata online. Similarly, the `distribution_id` key identifies the dataset with a URI. This will be linked to the dataset by means of the DCAT-AP property `dcat:distribution`³¹. The configuration links to the INI file that contains the metadata to generate as RDF compliant with the DCAT-AP as previously described.

As for other components, the Metadata manager enables access to the metadata generated for download and removal through HTTP(s) API made available by its REST module. The GET is structured in the following way:

²⁷ <https://op.europa.eu/en/web/eu-vocabularies/dcat-ap>

²⁸ The platform shall enable the production and management of machine readable, standardised metadata in compliance with the reference metadata definition vocabularies.

²⁹ The platform shall host and make available the standardised dataset metadata, to allow other data providers and external (open) data portals/catalogues to discover and harvest the published metadata.

³⁰ The platform shall produce RDF-based metadata associated with the produced RDF datasets.

³¹ The prefix `dcat:` stands for the namespace `http://www.w3.org/ns/dcat#`.

```
GET /metadata-mgr/<graph_id>
```

In the request above the path parameter <graph_id> has to be replaced with the identifier of the graph, e.g. **RMLMappinghydrolakes**, which is specified in the JSON object provided as input to the Metadata manager component.

A specific RDF serialisation of a graph can be obtained via content negotiation. For example, the following request performed with cURL specify the N-Triples serialisation in the Accept header.

```
curl -H "Accept: application/n-triples" \  
http://localhost:5000/metadata-mgr/RMLMappinghydrolakes
```

In the request above the endpoint `localhost:5000` should be replaced with the address of the server hosting the WHOW Toolkit.

Similarly, an RDF graph can be removed from those available for download from the Metadata manager by means of HTTP DELETE request, that is

```
DELETE /metadata-mgr/<graph_id>
```

3.2.7 Validator

The Validator is the Toolkit component designed and implemented to perform the validation of data and metadata. This is done by applying the SHACL shapes of the SEMIC's specification³². This validation uses all shapes (base, vocabularies, recommended properties, and ranges) for testing the compliance of metadata produced by the toolkit against the DCAT-AP version 2.0.1 specification. Then, if the SHACL based validation is passed then a Metadata Quality Assurance (MQA) is performed. For this the Validator implements the MQA methodology proposed by the official portal for European data³³. Hence, the Validator computes the scores for each indicator associated with the different dimensions (i.e. Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, Reusability, and Contextuality). Following the same rationale as the portal for European data, the ultimate rating is determined through four distinct rating groups, and the correlation between points and rating categories. In the MQA, the portrayal of the rating exclusively relies on these categories. The four groups of rating are reported in Table 1.

Table 1. Groups of rating for the MQA.

RATING	RANGE OF POINTS
Excellent	351 - 405
Good	221 – 350
Sufficient	121 – 220

³² <https://github.com/SEMICeu/DCAT-AP/releases/tag/v2.0.1>

³³ <https://data.europa.eu/mqa/methodology?locale=en>

The implementation of the MQA of the portal for European data within the toolkit allows the Validator to raise an error message in case the rating of the DCAT-AP associated with an RDF distribution of a dataset is below a given acceptance threshold. Accordingly, the publication activity is only carried out in case the Validator does not raise any error. Such a publication activity allows the toolkit to upload the RDF distribution in (i) a provided triplestore for accessing the data via SPARQL and (ii) a provided storage for enabling download. Additionally, the DCAT-AP compliant metadata are uploaded in the data catalogue. In the specific case of WHOW there are two data providers (i.e. ISPRA and ARIA) whose data catalogue are then harvested by the Italian National Data Catalogue³⁴, which in turn is harvested by the European Data Catalogue³⁵. The latter finally computes the MQA for each data catalogue at national level by means of the MQA tool.

The core module of the Validator component contains the class `SHACLValidator` that performs what described before when its method `do_job` is invoked. The synopsis of such a method is the following:

```
do_job(self, input: ValidatorInput, *args, **kwargs) -> dict:
```

The input is an instance of the class `ValidatorInput` whose objective is to provide a reference (i.e. a URI) to the RDF graph containing the metadata to validate. The output of the method invocation is a dictionary that provides information about the validation in terms of: (i) compliance of the metadata with the SHACL shapes of the SEMIC's specification and (ii) scores for each indicator associated with the different dimensions (i.e. Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, Reusability, and Contextuality) according to the MQA.

The Validator component addresses the requirements FR-11³⁶ its related sub-requirements as elicited in the Deliverable 4.1 for architectural design [1]

The functionalities provided by the `SHACLValidator` class can be accessed through the WebSocket interface implemented in the corresponding module of the Validator component. The input required by the WebSocket interface is a JSON message that contains a list of URI referring to RDF graphs providing metadata to validate as in the following example.

```
[ "https://www.example.org/graph1",
  "https://www.example.org/graph2",
  "https://www.example.org/graphN" ]
```

The output of the validation is made available via REST API. It is possible to access the result of a validation through a GET request like the following.

```
GET /validator?graph=<graph_uri>
```

³⁴ <https://dati.gov.it/>

³⁵ <https://data.europa.eu/>

³⁶ The platform shall support the validation of data for quality assessment purposes of the Knowledge Graph (using languages such as SHAC).

In the request above a value should be associated with the query parameter `graph_id`. Such a value is a URI that is used to identify the RDF graph associated with the validation output. The result of this request is a JSON object providing all the scores of the validation dimensions (i.e. Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, Reusability, and Contextuality). If multiple validations are performed for the same URI then the output of the validation for the given metadata graph is always replaced by the last one.

The output of a validation can be removed by means of a DELETE request over HTTP(s) like the following.

```
DELETE /validator?graph=<graph_uri>
```

3.2.8 Multilingual manager

The Multilingual manager is the component of the WHOW Toolkit that allows machine-translation of knowledge graphs. This is applied to literals only, i.e. the values associated with annotation properties (e.g. `rdfs:label`, `rdfs:comment`, etc.) or datatype properties.

The core module provide a class `MultilingualManager`, which is implements the interface `ToolkitComponent` by specialising the `do_job` method in order to accept as input: (i) a knowledge graph; (ii) a list of properties to use for selecting literals to process for translation; (iii) a source language; and (iv) a target language. All those parameters are contained in an object of the class `MultilingualManagerInput`, which is actually passed as input argument to the `do_job` method as shown below.

```
do_job(self, input: MultilingualManagerInput, *args, **kwargs) -> Graph:
```

The method returns a graph that contains the triples with a given subject, a selected target annotation or datatype property, and the literal resulting from the machine-translation.

By default `MultilingualManager` uses DeepL³⁷ as an external service for machine translation by querying such a service via its API REST. Nevertheless, it is possible to configure the class in order to use eTranslation³⁸ instead. The Multilingual manager component addresses the requirement FR-34³⁹ of architectural design.

The interaction via WebSocket interface is possible thanks to its API that accepts a JSON message like the following:

```
[
  {
    "id": "hydrolakes",
    "uri": "https://w3id.org/italia/lombardia/data/distribution/kr6i-f553-ttl",
    "properties": [
      "http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#label",
      "http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#comment",
      "https://w3id.org/italia/env/onto/top/name"
    ],
    "source_language": "it",
    "target_languages": ["en", "fr", "de"]
  }
]
```

³⁷ <https://www.deepl.com/translator>

³⁸ https://commission.europa.eu/resources-partners/etranslation_en

³⁹ The user shall be able to select his/her preferred language for ease of navigation of the Knowledge Graph.

```
}  
]
```

The message contains a list of objects that describe how to process a knowledge graph (referred to the `uri` key and identified by the `uri` key) for translating literals associated with a given set of properties (i.e. the `properties` key) from a `source_language` as IETF BCP 47⁴⁰ language tag to a list of `target_languages` as IETF BCP 47 language tags. The output message of the WebSocket API is a JSON list that contains the resulting graphs in terms of their internal ID and the URI that can be used for retrieving the graph via HTTP REST API. An example of output is the following.

```
[  
  {"id": "hydrolakes",  
   "uri": "https://someuri/hydrolakes"}  
]
```

Then, it is possible to access the resulting RDF graph in different serialisations (i.e. Turtle, RDF/XML, N-Triples, N3, and JSON-LD) with a GET request like the following.

```
GET /translator/<graph_id>
```

A graph can be removed from the component with a DELETE request like the following.

```
DELETE /translator/<graph_id>
```

3.2.9 Triplestore manager

The RDF graphs can be published into a triplestore that enables querying via the SPARQL protocol and language. The Triplestore manager is the component of the WHOW Toolkit designed and implemented to cope with these functionalities. More specifically, the Triplestore manager addresses the requirements FR-04⁴¹, FR-05⁴², and FRs from 37 to 43⁴³. The core of the Triplestore manager is implemented by the class `VirtuosoTriplestoreManager`, which leverages on OpenLink Virtuoso⁴⁴ as an RDF storage and SPARQL engine. It specialises the `do_job` method in order to the following way:

```
do_job(self, input: TriplestoreInput, *args, **kwargs) -> dict:
```

⁴⁰ <https://www.rfc-editor.org/bcp/bcp47.txt>

⁴¹ The platform shall include data storage capabilities for the physical storage and management of the knowledge graph.

⁴² The TripleStore shall organise data in named graphs.

⁴³ Those functional requirements are classified as *Query-based data consumption*.

⁴⁴ <https://virtuoso.openlinksw.com/>

The instance of the `TriplestoreInput` class provides the following parameters as input:

- The name of the graph to populate in the triplestore. If no name is provided then the default graph is selected as a policy;
- The list of the URIs that refer to the RDF graphs to load in the triplestores.

The `do_job` method is invoked by the `WebSocket` module, which in turn receives a JSON object that represents a list of instances `TriplestoreInput`, like the following.

```
[
  {"id": "hydrolakes",
   "uri": "https://anygraphuri"}
]
```

Once loaded a graph can be queried via the SPARQL endpoint exposed by Virtuoso.

The REST module of the Triplestore manager wraps the API of Virtuoso for querying RDF graphs with the SPARQL 1.1 language⁴⁵

3.3 Code availability and licence

The WHOW Toolkit is publicly available on a repository owned by the WHOW Team on GitHub⁴⁶ and is released under the Apache 2.0 licence.

4. Knowledge graph

The WHOW-KG was developed to cope with three selected use cases identified in the context of the WHOW project with domain experts and data providers. Those use cases are: (i) Contaminants in marine waters (UC1), (ii) Water quality for human consumption (UC2), and (iii) Meteorological extreme events (UC3). The first use case, i.e. Contaminants in marine waters, aims at modelling ontologies and creating linked open data on human exposure to chemicals and biological contaminants in marine waters, ingestion of

⁴⁵ <https://www.w3.org/TR/sparql11-query/>

⁴⁶ <https://github.com/whow-project/architecture/tree/main/whow-toolkit>

contaminated fish products, and airborne exposure, such as *Ostreopsis Ovata*⁴⁷. The second use case, i.e. Water quality and for human consumption, focuses on generating ontologies and linked open data for modelling and representing quality of surface and ground waters as well as drinking water quality parameters and values, measured by compliance with the EU Directive 2020/2184⁴⁸ on the quality of water intended for human consumption. Finally, the third use, i.e., Meteorological Extreme events, is about modelling ontologies and linked open data for representing meteorological phenomena, alteration of the hydrological cycle and agriculture industries. More details about the use cases can be found by interested readers in a public deliverable [9] of the project.

4.1 Material

The aforementioned use cases were defined along with the identification of pertinent core open datasets by means of a co-creation programme organised within the scope of the WHOW project. Hence, 77 participants actively contributed to the programme. The group of co-creators included domain experts, stakeholders, practitioners, and data providers from both public and private organisations located in the EU. The full list of datasets identified can be consulted in a corresponding project deliverable [10]. From this list, we selected high-priority datasets that are currently used for designing and generating the WHOW-KG. The selection was done in compliance with the following criteria: (i) relevance to the use cases; (ii) open licence associated with the dataset; and (iii) data availability for the years spanning mainly from 2018 to 2021. For some datasets, the time period is even longer starting from 1999 to 2023. In general, time span of reference 2018-2021 is a requirement defined in the project and contributors of the co-creation programme. The identified datasets, all available as CSV, are reported in Table 2 with an identifier, short description, data provider, and supported use cases.

Table 2. Datasets selected for the creation of the WHOW-KG⁴⁹.

⁴⁷ *Ostreopsis Ovata* is a well known genus of free-living dinoflagellates found in marine environments that is frequently associated with phenomena of human intoxication.

⁴⁸ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/dir/2020/2184/oj>

⁴⁹ The input datasets provided by ISPRA are available on their open data catalogue available at <https://dati.isprambiente.it/en/>. Instead, those provided by ARIA are available on GitHub at <https://github.com/whow-project/datasets>.

ID	Description	Provider	Use Cases	ID	Description	Provider	Use Cases
D1	Observations from tide gauges Network	ISPRA	UC2	D10	Analytical data of lake water bodies	ARIA	UC2
D2	Wave motion data	ISPRA	UC2	D11	Quality parameters of drinking waters	ARIA	UC2
D3	Soil consumption indicators	ISPRA	UC3	D12	Analytical data of undergroundwater	ARIA	UC2
D4	Repertory of mitigation measures for National Soil Protection	ISPRA	UC3	D13	Height of the lakes	ARIA	UC2
D5	Bathing water quality indicators	ISPRA	UC1	D14	Description of Health Protection Agencies	ARIA	UC2
D6	Ostreopsis ovata	ISPRA	UC1	D15	Hospital stay and access rates	ARIA	UC2
D7	Pesticides in waters	ISPRA	UC1	D16	Drug consumption rate	ARIA	UC2
D8	Administrative places in Italy	ISPRA	UC1-3	D17	Infectious diseases rates by sex and age	ARIA	UC2
D9	Analytical data of river water bodies, including flow rate	ARIA	UC2	D18	Meteo observations and weather stations	ARIA	UC3

4.2 Method

The methodology we used for constructing the WHOW-KG is inspired by the one defined in [11] and relies on eXtreme Design [12] (XD) for ontology modelling. XD emphasises the reuse of ontology design patterns [13] (ODPs) into an iterative and incremental process. More interestingly, XD is a collaborative methodology that fosters the cooperation among multiple actors with different roles (e.g. knowledge engineers, domain experts, etc.) to make sure all the modelling requirements are first captured and then effectively covered. Hence, we opted for XD since it fits our collaborative setting based on the co-creation programme. Furthermore, there is evidence in literature [14] that the reuse of ODPs (i) speeds up the ontology design process, (ii) eases design choices, (iii) produces more effective results in terms of ontology quality, and (iv) boosts interoperability.

Figure 8. Methodology implemented for constructing the WHOW-KG.

Figure 8 shows the methodology implemented for constructing the WHOW-KG. It is worth noticing that the methodology is fully supported by the WHOW Toolkit.

4.2.1 Ontology design

In such a figure, the activities named *requirement collection*, *test design*, *ontology module development*, and *ontology testing* come from XD and focus on ontology design. The requirement collection activity aims at eliciting the requirements as *competency questions* [15] (CQs). CQs are natural language questions conveying the ontological commitment expected from a knowledge graph (KG) and drive both ontology modelling and validation. In fact, on the one hand CQs are a means for ontology development. On the other, they can be converted to formal queries in order to assess the effectiveness of the resulting KG to cope with the requirements. We implemented the validation into the *ontology testing* activity. This was done by converting defined CQs into SPARQL and executing the latter as unit tests with toy data following the solution defined in [11]. The ontology development we applied is modular (cf. activity named *ontology module development*) allowing us to generate a set of networked ontologies. Each ontology of the network is a separate module designed with the purpose of minimising coupling with other ontology modules and maximising the internal cohesion of its conceptualisation. The re-use of external ontologies and ODPs was done by applying both the direct and indirect approach [16]. Direct reuse is about embedding individual entities or importing implementations of ODPs or other ontologies in the network, thus making it highly dependent on them. Instead, indirect reuse is about applying relevant entities and patterns from external ontologies as templates, by reproducing them in the ontologies of the network and providing possible extensions. We opted for direct re-use in case of widely adopted vocabularies, such as SKOS, the Time ontology available in the Italian national catalogue of semantic assets for public administrations⁵⁰, aligned with the W3C time ontology, and the top-level⁵¹ (TOP) and environmental monitoring facilities⁵² (EMF)

⁵⁰ <https://schema.gov.it>

⁵¹ <https://github.com/whow-project/semantic-assets/blob/main/ispra-ontology-network/top/latest/top.rdf>

⁵²

<https://github.com/whow-project/semantic-assets/blob/main/ispra-ontology-network/inspire-mf/latest/inspire-mf.rdf>

ontologies of the Linked ISPRa project⁵³. TOP is used as a top-level ontology that provides general concepts and relations, whilst EMF provides core domain concepts and relations for modelling environmental monitoring data. On the contrary, we opted for the indirect approach for re-using patterns and to support interoperability with other pertinent ontologies, e.g. SSN/SOSA⁵⁴ \cite{Haller2019}. The latter case was realised by means of alignments axioms, such as `rdfs:subClassOf` and `owl:equivalentClass` in dedicated alignment ontologies.

4.2.2 Linked Open Data production

Once the ontology network is modelled the next steps in the methodology aims at populating the KG with Linked Open Data (LOD) gathered from the identified input data sources (cf. Table 1). The LOD production was performed by means of declarative mappings and workflows enabled by the WHOW Toolkit. Hence, in the activity *mapping development* we defined those mappings by means of the RDF Mapping Language⁵⁵ [6] (RML), which extends the W3C-standardised mapping language R2RML⁵⁶ for mapping to an RDF kind of structured data source. All the RML mapping rules defined are available on the project's GitHub repository⁵⁷. These mappings were processed by the Triplifier component of the WHOW Toolkit that relies on pyRML⁵⁸. The latter, as mentioned in [Section 3.2.4](#), is a lightweight Python engine for processing RML files designed and implemented in the context of the project. Data validation was then performed by using the Validator component of the Toolkit, which, in turns, relies on SHACL shapes. The activities related to data production are meant to be executed in a decentralised and distributed fashion in which different data providers might use their data and RML mapping rules independently.

We produced the Linked Open Data from the data provided by ISPRa and ARIA, as reported in Table 1. This was done by customising and executing the workflows designed with WHOW Toolkit as described in [Section 3](#). Figure 9 shows the configuration we applied to the WHOW Toolkit for both ARIA and ISPRa. Namely, the Toolkit components are linked to the external platforms or packages they rely on for providing their functionalities. The Data ingester collects data from Socrata⁵⁹ and a distributed file system in case of ARIA and ISPRa, respectively. The preprocessor is configured for applying UTF-8 conversion and charset normalisation for both ARIA and ISPRa. The Triplifier is based on pyRML for both ARIA and ISPRa. Again, for both ARIA and ISPRa, the Metadata manager and Triplestore manager use OpenLink Virtuoso⁶⁰ for retrieving existing metadata and storing generated data and metadata, respectively. Finally, pySHACL is used as the SHACL-based validator both in case of ARIA and ISPRa.

⁵³ <https://dati.isprambiente.it/>

⁵⁴ <https://www.w3.org/TR/vocab-ssn/>

⁵⁵ <https://rml.io/specs/rml/>

⁵⁶ <https://www.w3.org/TR/r2rml/>

⁵⁷ <https://github.com/whow-project/datasets>

⁵⁸ <https://github.com/anuzzolese/pyrml/>

⁵⁹ <https://dev.socrata.com/>

⁶⁰ <https://virtuoso.openlinksw.com/>

Figure 9. Configuration of the WHOW Toolkit used for generating the WHOW-KG for ARIA and ISPRA.

Based on the workflow enabled by the WHOW Toolkit we generated two linked open datasets part of the WHOW-KG, that is the one from the data provided by ISPRA and the other from the data provided by ARIA. The ownership of the generated linked datasets along with their corresponding maintenance effort is kept by the data providers. This fits the requirement of WHOW to create and maintain a knowledge graph following a decentralised and distributed paradigm (cf. FR-02⁶¹ and NFR-01⁶² elicited in Deliverable 4.1 [1]). In this scenario new data providers might publish their data as linked open data compliant with the WHOW ontology network by using their preferred persistent URIs and setting up their own SPARQL endpoint, thus maximising the sustainability of the WHOW-KG. With this regard, ISPRA identified <https://w3id.org/italia/env/ld/> as its reference namespace. Accordingly, the pattern <https://w3id.org/italia/env/ld/type/id> was applied for producing RDF resources, where *type* and *id* are placeholders for an entity type (e.g. water-sample) and its local identifier (e.g. 45.60555-13.72195), respectively. The RDF data produced by ISPRA can be queried through their dedicated SPARQL endpoint⁶³ and are available as a single dump on Zenodo⁶⁴ for download with a CC-BY 4.0 International licence.

Similarly, ARIA identified <https://w3id.org/italia/lombardia/data/> as its reference namespace. Also in this case, the pattern <https://w3id.org/italia/lombardia/data/type/id> was applied for

⁶¹ The platform shall be able to use data from other data providers than the ones already included in WHOW.

⁶² The platform should be scalable in order to accommodate the joining of additional providers to the overall knowledge graph.

⁶³ <https://dati.isprambiente.it/sparql>

⁶⁴ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7916383>

producing RDF resources with the same rationale as before. Again, the RDF data produced by ARIA can be queried via SPARQL⁶⁵ and are available on Zenodo⁶⁶ for download with a CC0 licence.

Finally, three controlled vocabularies were produced from the data provided by ARIA. This vocabularies provides term definitions for: (i) chemical substances⁶⁷; (ii) diseases⁶⁸; and (iii) water indicators⁶⁹.

In the case of controlled vocabularies we opted for a namespace not depending on the specific data provider, i.e. <https://w3id.org/whow/controlled-vocabulary/>. This namespace was used for producing RDF resources by applying the pattern <https://w3id.org/whow/controlled-vocabulary/name/id>, where *name* and *id* are placeholders for the vocabulary name (e.g. chemical-substances) and term local identifier (e.g. cas-102851-06-9), respectively. The controlled vocabularies are available on Zenodo⁷⁰ and can be queried via SPARQL⁷¹. The WHOW-KG counts of 152,246,711 triples in the linked dataset generated by ISPRA, 113,190,050 triples in the linked dataset generated by ARIA, and 16,350 triples available in the controlled vocabularies, thus generating a total of 265,453,111 triples. Table 2 reports the number of triples generated for each RDF dataset.

Table 3. Datasets part of WHOW-KG with their corresponding number of triples.

ID	Description	Triples	ID	Description	Triples
D1	Observations from tide gauges Network	527,423	D10	Analytical data of lake water bodies	1,409,794
D2	Wave motion data	135,753	D11	Quality parameters of drinking waters	2,734,537
D3	Soil consumption indicators	57,528,925	D12	Analytical data of underground water	5,959,926
D4	Repertory of mitigation measures for National Soil Protection	2,290,973	D13	Height of the lakes	57,924
D5	Bathing water quality indicators	1,669,340	D14	Description of Health Protection Agencies	385
D6	Ostreopsis ovata	103,383	D15	Hospital stay and access rates	483,843
D7	Pesticides in waters	89,635,028	D16	Drug consumption rate	151,489
D8	Administrative places in Italy	355,886	D17	Infectious diseases rates by sex and age	464,532
D9	Analytical data of river water bodies, including flow rate	10,638,603	D18	Meteo observations and weather stations	91,772,860

⁶⁵ <https://lod.dati.lombardia.it/sparql>

⁶⁶ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7916732>

⁶⁷

<https://github.com/whow-project/semantic-assets/blob/main/controlled-vocabularies/chemical-substances/chemical-substances.ttl>

⁶⁸ <https://github.com/whow-project/semantic-assets/blob/main/controlled-vocabularies/diseases/diseases.ttl>

⁶⁹

<https://github.com/whow-project/semantic-assets/blob/main/controlled-vocabularies/water-indicators/water-indicators.ttl>

⁷⁰ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7919460>

⁷¹ <https://sem Scout.istc.cnr.it/sparql/>

4.3 Usage examples

The WHOW-KG can answer a variety of questions that encompass the three use cases reported in [Section 4.1](#). For example, it would be possible to retrieve the contaminants recorded in a water body used for human consumption (UC2). A possible question is the following:

What was the concentration of reactive silicates observed for the lake Endine over time?

This question can be converted into the following SPARQL query:

```
SELECT ?obs ?time ?value ?unit
WHERE{
  ?obs a wm:WaterPhysicoChemicalParameterObservation ;
    emf:hasFeatureOfInterest data-lwb:endine ;
    wm:hasWaterObservableProperty data-op:1344-09-8 ;
    wm:hasResult/top:value ?value ;
    wm:hasResult/top:hasUnitOfMeasure/top:name ?unit ;
    emf:generationTime/top:time ?time .
}
ORDER BY ?time
```


Figure 10. The RDF graph that answers the question: *What was the concentration of reactive silicates observed for Lake Endine over time?*

A snapshot of the result set resulting from the execution of the SPARQL query above against the endpoint exposed by ARIA, is the RDF graph depicted in Figure 10. In this graph the entity Water Observation

8728afd4 is a `wm:Water-Physico-ChemicalParameter-Observation` as defined by the Water Monitoring module⁷² and is connected to: (i) a feature of interest, which is the Lake Endine typed as `hydro:LakeWaterBody`; (ii) an observation result, i.e. `Water Observation 8728afd4 result` typed as a `w-mon:ObservationValue`, which is associated with a specific literal value (i.e. 11.3) and a unit of measure (i.e. mg/l); (iii) a generation time for the observation which is the `ispra-top:TemporalEntity` identified by the entity `2020-08-27` with its corresponding literal value.

Another possible question related to UC1 might be focused on retrieving the observation of biological agents like the *ostreopsis ovata* in marine water bodies. An example of this case is the question: {\em What were the biological agents with their associated concentration recorded over time for the Adriatic sea?} This question can be converted into the following SPARQL query:

```
SELECT ?obs ?bioagent ?link ?time
WHERE{
  ?obs a w-mon:WaterBiologicalQualityParameterObservation;
        ispra-emf:generationTime ?time;
        ispra-emf:hasFeatureOfInterest data:adriatic-sea;
        w-mon:hasResult ?res;
        w-mon:hasBiologicalAgent ?bioagent .
  OPTIONAL{?bioagent owl:sameAs ?link}
```

A snapshot of the result set resulting from the execution of the SPARQL query above against the endpoint exposed by ISPRA⁷³ is the RDF graph depicted in Figure 11. In this case, the entity `Water Observation 0076b974` is a `w-mon:Water-Biological-Quality-Parameter-Observation` and is connected to: (i) a feature of interest, which is the `Adriatic sea` typed as `hydro:MarineWaterBody`; (ii) an observation result, i.e. `Water Observation 0076b974 result` typed as a `w-mon:Observation-Value`, which is associated with the value `160 cell per litre`; (iii) a generation time for the observation which is the `ispra-top:TemporalEntity` identified by the entity `2020-08-04` with its corresponding literal value; (iv) the biological agent represented by the *Ostreopsis ovata*, which is typed as `w-mon:BiologicalAgent`.

⁷² <https://w3id.org/whow/onto/water-monitoring>

⁷³ <https://t.ly/UY9BF>

Figure 11. The RDF graph that answers the question: What were the biological agents with their associated concentration recorded over time for the Adriatic sea?

This kind of observational data on water quality can be linked to data about the average rate of hospitalisation for the same geographical area that reports diseases.

A possible example of SPARQL query that addresses this case is presented below and provides the average accesses in the hospitals located in Lombardy, Italy associated with time and disease recorded. This query can be executed against the endpoint exposed by ARIA⁷⁴. Additional examples for all use cases can be found on GitHub⁷⁵.

```

SELECT ?calc ?value ?disease ?year
WHERE{
  ?calc a hm:HospitalCareIndicatorCalculation ;
        hm:doneForHCIndicator indicator:average-total-number-access ;
        hm:hasHealthcareIndicatorValue/ispra-top:value ?value ;
        ispra-top:atTime/ispra-top:year ?year ;
        hm:ofClinicalCohort/hm:affectedBy ?disease
}

```

Finally, for both ARIA and ISPRA, a LodView⁷⁶ instance has been deployed on top of the Triplestore manager component. This allows one to browse the WHOW-KG either with HTML views enabled by a Web browser or HTTP(s) requests associated with machine-readable formats through content negotiation. Figure 12 shows the architectural deployment applied both in case of ARIA and ISPRA. In this deployment the Triplestore component of the WHOW Toolkit queries the SPARQL endpoint exposed by OpenLink Virtuoso when

⁷⁴ <https://t.ly/oP8Xp>

⁷⁵ <https://github.com/whow-project/datasets>

⁷⁶ <https://lodview.it/>

triggered through its REST API by the LodView instance. The latter sends HTTP(s) requests to the Triplestore component when a GET request comes in from an agent, either human or artificial. All the incoming HTTP(s) requests are always mediated by the w3id.org service⁷⁷, which provides a secure, permanent URL redirection service for Web applications. This service is run by the W3C Permanent Identifier Community Group. This configuration addresses the requirements FR 18-36 elicited in the Deliverable 4.1[1].

Figure 12. Interaction with the WHOW-KG.

Figure 13. HTML (a) and Turtle (b) visualisations of the entity <https://w3id.org/italia/env/ld/water-observation/0076b974d176c9c8887587ae10955f2f>.

Figure 13(a) shows the HTML visualisation of an RDF entity available in the part of the WHOW-KG published by ISPRa. Instead, Figure 13(b) shows the Turtle serialisation of the same entity. This can be obtained with an

⁷⁷ <https://github.com/perma-id/w3id.org>

HTTP(s) request that specifies the mime-type (i.e. text/turtle) in the Accept header explicitly. The following is an example of a request performed with cURL.

```
curl -kL -H "Accept: text/turtle" \  
https://w3id.org/italia/env/ld/water-observation/0076b974d176c9c8887587ae10955f2f
```

5 Conclusions

This document presents the result of the implementation and deployment of the WHOW Architecture obtained for Milestone #8 (The technical architecture is deployed). The implementation and deployment relies on the analysis and design presented in the Deliverable 4.1⁷⁸ [1] and addressing the Milestone #7 (Design of the technical services for knowledge graph management is finalised). Hence, we first recall general concepts on the high-level architecture we designed, then we describe the implementation of such an architecture, which consists of a software platform. The latter includes: (i) a set of reusable components for knowledge graph creation and management, called the WHOW Toolkit, that we implemented in the context of the WHOW project; and (ii) a novel semantic knowledge graph for water quality and sanitation. The WHOW Toolkit and knowledge graph are further integrated in a broader software deployment that includes existing open source solutions we reused for providing interaction capabilities to users, being them either humans or applications. By interaction capabilities we mean accessing, querying, and visualising the knowledge graph as well as using the services provided by the WHOW Toolkit. These are exposed through REST API or WebSocket interfaces depending on specific cases that we detail in next chapters and sections.

⁷⁸ <https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.6685696>

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